

Research Article

Problems Facing Fish Farming Business in Kwara State: A Case Study of Four Local Government Areas

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Abstract

This study assessed the problems facing fish farmers in four (4) Local Government Areas of Kwara State. Thirty (30) fish farmers based on availability were surveyed in this study. The stratified sampling technique was used to carry out the survey. The outcome of the survey exercise carried out revealed that water shortages during dry season, lack of capital, disease and pest infestation and high cost of fish feed were identified as part of the major problems that affected fish farming business in the study area. The study recommends the use of supplementary feed for catfish such as maggot and other locally formulated feed as an alternative to foreign feeds which are very expensive. In view of this, the study further recommends that fish farmers in Kwara State should attend trainings on maggot production, preservation and utilization.

Key words: fish, farming, problems, government, state, business

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Introduction

Fish is one of the most diverse groups of animals that live and breathe in water by means of gills, known to man with more than 20,000 species. There are more species of fish than the other vertebrate (FAO, 1997). The activity of fish farming in Nigeria started about 50 years ago. It began with the installment of a compact experimental station at Onikan, Lagos and an industrial farm about 20 hectares at Panyam in Plateau State by Federal Government. This generated a lot of attraction to fish farming and other levels of government and some private establishments became

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involved (Olagunju *et al.*, 2007). It is estimated that Africa produced 7.3 million tonnes in 2003, and about 80% of this is produced by just two countries which are Nigeria and Egypt (FAO, 2011).

Nigerians are high consumers of fish and offer the largest market for fish and fishery product in Africa (Olaoye and Oloruntoba, 2011). The fisheries subsector occupies a unique position in the agricultural sector of the Nigerian economy as it contributes about one-tenth of the GDP to the sector (FDF, 2008). Its prospect continues to increase due to the huge gap between fish demand and supply which leaves a shortfall of about 680,000 metric tonnes of fish annually necessitating government importation of fish worth ₦97 billion annually (Adekunle, 2013). This continuous increase in import bills for fish products is not a good omen for the Nigerian economy and thus creates opportunities for fish farmers to leverage on. However, despite the huge gap between demand and supply, fish farmers in Nigeria seems not to be able to fully maximize the prospect in the sector due to the underdevelopment and use of value addition initiatives (Adefalu *et al.*, 2013), as many fish farmers are still experiencing low profit margin or even inability to break even. Fish farmers are now experiencing pressures that come not only from lower selling prices, but also from higher input cost (EU, 2011).

Fish farming generates employment directly and indirectly in terms of people employed in the production of fishing output and other allied business, it also generates income for all categories of people involved in fish farming and thus contributes to the national income. When compared with livestock, it requires less space, time, money and has a higher feed conserving rate. Adereti *et al.* (2006) stated that the inability of production to meet demand can be attributed to a number of constraints which include inadequate capital, high cost of feed and inadequate supply of quality fingerlings. Therefore, this study sought to provide information on the major problems facing fish farming business in Kwara State so as to suggest possible ways out in making fish farming a lucrative business in the State.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in Asa, Ilorin East, Ilorin South and Ifelodun Local Government Areas of Kwara State. The State shares boundaries with Oyo, Osun and Ekiti to the South, Kogi and Niger to the North, Kogi to the east and Republic of Benin on the west side. Kwara State has sixteen Local Government Areas. Kwara State is located in the North-Central geopolitical zone (middle-belt) of Nigeria in the areas that extend roughly from latitude (60301 to 110051) north of the equator and longitude (2051 to 70451) east of the prime meridian. This area is largely located in the savannah region of Nigeria. It is an ecological transition zone between the arid north and the moist south with temperature fluctuating between 30^oC and 37^oC in the year and rainfall of 1000 to 1500 mm annually. The study area has two distinct climatic seasons, namely wet (Rainy) and dry (Harmattan) seasons. The rainfall across the two seasons extends between November and February. This climatic condition as well as fertile soil makes the State favorable for arable crop production such as rice, millet, yam, cowpea etc. (KWARA MANR, 2012).

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Data collection

This research work was conducted to investigate the constraints of fish farmers in four Local Government Areas of Kwara State. A stratified sampling technique was employed in administering a closed-ended questionnaire. The survey exercise was based on the number of available farmers into fish production in the selected LGAs. Fish farmers were randomly selected from four different Local Government Areas of the State namely Asa, Ilorin South, Ilorin East and Ifelodun.

Data were collected on various socio-economic characteristics output which include age, marital status, gender, household size, years of farming experience and level of education. More so, the constraints facing fish farming business in the State were also contained in the administered questionnaires to the fish farmers. Information pertaining to the problems confronting fish farmers as contained in the administered questionnaires were provided with three different options which stated very serious, serious and not a problem.

Statistical tool

Data obtained from the respondents into fish farming business in the four Local Government Areas of Kwara State were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis involving frequency counts and percentage. The SPSS statistical package of version 25.0.0.0 was used for the data computation.

Results and Discussion

Socio-economic characteristics

Age

Thirty fish farmers were sourced based on availability within the four Local Government Areas of Kwara State. Out of these 30 fish farmers, 4 of them representing 13.33% were in the age bracket of 21 - 30 years, 12 of them representing 40% fell within the age bracket of 31 – 40 years, 9 of them representing 30% fell within the age bracket of 41 – 50 years and 5 of them representing 16.67% fell within the age bracket of 50 years and above. This signifies that youths within the age bracket of 31 - 40 years of age dominated the fish farming business in the four Local Government Areas surveyed in Kwara State.

Marital status

Among the 30 fish farmers surveyed in this study, 24 of them representing 80% were found to be married, 5 of them representing 16.67% were single and 1 of them representing 3.33% was found to be a widow. This signifies that majority of the fish farmers in the area surveyed were married.

Gender

Out of the 30 fish farmers who responded to the questionnaires, 25 of them representing 83.33% were males while the remaining 5 representing 16.67% were females. This signifies that there are more male fish farmers than female fish farmers in fish farming business in the surveyed area.

Household size

Out of the 30 fish farmers surveyed in this study, 15 of them representing 50% have a household size of 0 – 5 people, 9 of them representing 30% have a household size of 6 – 10 people, 1 of them representing 3.33% have a household size of 11 – 15 people while the remaining 5 representing 16.67% of the fish farmers failed to declare their household size. This signifies that majority of the fish farmers involved in the study had a household size of 0 – 5 people.

Years of experience in fish farming

Twenty-seven (27) out of the 30 fish farmers surveyed representing 90% had between 1 - 10 years of fish farming experience while the remaining 3 fish farmers representing 10% had between 11 - 20 years of fish farming experience. This simply shows that almost all the farmers involved in the study area had between 1 – 10 years of fish farming experience.

Educational level

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were involved in the survey, 22 of them representing 73.33% had tertiary education, 4 of them representing 13.33% had high school education, while 1 respondent each representing 3.33% had primary education, adult education and no formal education, respectively. Also, one of the respondents representing 3.33% declined to give information related to his educational status. Almost all the fish farmers in the study area had tertiary education.

Constraints facing fish farming

Land acquisition

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were involved in the survey, 19 of them representing 63.33% reported that land acquisition was not a problem, 8 of them representing 26.67% reported that land acquisition was a serious problem, 1 of them representing 3.33% reported that land acquisition was a very serious problem to him while 2 of them representing 6.67% failed to respond. This implies that majority of the fish farmers do not have a problem in acquiring land for fish farming.

Access to labour

Out of the 30 fish farmers surveyed in this study, 24 of them representing 80% reported that having access to labour was not a problem, 3 of them representing 10% reported that having access to labour was a serious problem, 1 of them representing 3.33% reported that having access to labour was a very serious problem to him while 2 of them representing 6.67% failed to respond. This implies that labour was available in the surveyed area.

Lack of market availability for fish

Seventeen (17) out of the thirty fish farmers representing 56.67% reported that market availability for fish was not a problem to them, 8 of them representing 26.67% reported that market availability for fish was a serious problem, 3 of them representing 10% reported that market availability for fish was a very serious problem while 2 of them representing 6.67% failed to respond. This means that there is market availability for fish in the study area.

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Access to processing, preservation and storage facilities

Out of the 30 fish farmers surveyed in this study, 18 of them representing 60% reported that having access to processing, preservation and storage facilities was not a problem, 6 of them representing 20% reported that having access to processing, preservation and storage facilities was a serious problem, 3 of them representing 10% reported that having access to processing, preservation and storage facilities pose a very serious problem while 3 of them representing 10% failed to respond. This signifies that majority of the fish farmers have access to processing, preservation and storage facilities for their fish.

Lack of capital

Out of the 30 fish farmers surveyed in this study, 16 of them representing 53.33% reported that capital was a very serious problem, 11 of them representing 33.33% reported that capital was a serious problem, 1 of them representing 3.33% reported that capital was not a problem while 2 of them representing 6.67% failed to respond. This implies that most of the fish farmers lacked capital for their fish farming business.

High cost of quality fingerlings

Fourteen (14) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 46.67% reported that high cost of quality fingerlings was not a problem, 12 of them representing 40% reported that high cost of quality fingerlings was a serious problem, 2 of them representing 6.67% reported that high cost of quality fingerlings was a very serious problem while the remaining 2 representing 6.67% failed to respond. From this study, it is difficult to conclude if high cost of quality fingerlings posed a problem to the fish farmers having observed equal numbers of those that picked not a problem and was a problem.

High cost of construction equipment

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were involved in the study area, 14 of them representing 46.67% reported that high cost of construction equipment was not a problem, 8 of them representing 26.67% reported that high cost of construction was a serious problem, 5 of them representing 16.675 reported that high cost of construction was a very serious problem while 3 of them representing 10% failed to respond. This suggests that most fish farmers in the surveyed area used construction equipment that was relatively high to others who could not afford high cost of construction equipment befitting a fish farm site.

Market price fluctuation

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were involved in the study area, 10 of them representing 33.33% reported that market price fluctuation was a very serious problem, 17 of them representing 56.67% reported that market price fluctuation was a serious problem, 1 of them representing 3.33% reported that market fluctuation is not a problem while 2 of them representing 6.67% failed to respond. This means that larger percentage of the fish farmers did not allow the issue of price fluctuation to disturb their business.

High cost of fish feed

Eighteen (18) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 60% reported that high cost of fish feed was a serious problem, 9 of them representing 30% reported that high cost of fish feed was a very serious problem while 3 of them representing 10% failed to respond. This means that high cost of fish feed really affected their fish farming business. This finding on high cost of fish feed which affected fish farming business in the surveyed area was in agreement with the study of Adereti et al. (2006).

Water shortage during dry season

Out of the 30 fish farmers surveyed in this study, 13 of them representing 40% reported that water shortage during dry season was not a problem, 6 out of them representing 20% reported that water shortage during dry season was a serious problem, 10 of them representing 33.33% reported that water shortage during dry season was a very serious problem while 1 of them representing 3.33% failed to respond. This implies that a larger percentage of the fish farmers had issue with shortage of water during the dry season.

Disease and pest infestation

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were involved in the study area, 12 of them representing 36.67% reported that disease and pest infestation was not a problem, 14 of them representing 43.33% reported that disease and pest infestation was a serious problem, 2 of them representing 6.67% reported that disease and pest was a very serious problem while the remaining 2 representing 6.67% failed to respond. In conclusion, this means that larger percentage of the fish farmers had problem with disease and pest infestation in their fish farms.

Lack of technical know-how

Out of the 30 fish farmers surveyed in this study, 22 of them representing 73.33% reported that lack of technical know-how was not a problem, 4 of them representing 13.33% reported that lack of technical know-how was a serious problem, 2 of them representing 6.67% reported that lack of technical know-how was a very serious problem while 2 of them representing 6.67% failed to respond. The aspect of lack of technical know-how on how to do fish farming business was never a problem to the fish farmers in the study area.

Lack of accessible road leading to the fish farm

Twenty-four (24) out of the 30 fish farmers, representing 80% reported that lack of accessible road leading to the fish farm was not a problem, 3 of them representing 10% reported that lack of access road leading to the fish farm was a serious problem, 1 of them representing 3.33% reported that lack of access road leading to the fish farm was a very serious problem while 2 of them representing 6.67% failed to respond. This implies that majority of the fish farmers had accessible road leading to their fish farms which made sales of fish and transportation of materials easy for them.

Inability to access latest technologies on fish farming

The latest technologies in this subsection are those pertaining to improved fingerlings/juvenile and fish feeds which can be obtained through seminars or trainings. In respect of this survey, it was discovered that out of the 30 fish farmers involved in the study, 12 of them representing 40% reported that having access to latest technologies on fish farming was not a problem. Similarly, same was the situation for those that picked serious problem. Four (4) of them representing 13.33% reported that having access to latest technologies on fish farming was a very serious problem while 2 of them representing 6.67% failed to respond. It can be deduced that a larger percentage of the fish farmers reported that inability to have access to latest technologies on fish farming affected their business.

Conclusion and Recommendations

A survey was carried out in four Local Government Areas of Kwara State. The fish farmers were 30 in number comprising of youths within the age bracket of 31 – 40 years of age. Ninety (90) percent of these fish farmers claimed to have up to 1 – 10 years of experience in fish farming business. About 73.33% of these fish farmers claimed to study up to tertiary education level. The survey which was purposely carried out to investigate the problems facing fish farming business in the State identified lack of capital, disease and pest infestation, water shortage during dry season and high cost of fish feed among the major problems affecting fish farming business in Kwara State. In addition to these, the inaccessibility of the fish farmers to appropriate latest technologies and innovations such as improved fingerlings/juvenile and improved fish feeds were also discovered as problems affecting fish farming business.

These identified problems pose a serious threat in the general supply of fish today and in the near future to come. In view of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The production of supplementary feed for catfish such as maggot and any other locally formulated feed should be considered in the study area to reduce the cost of purchasing foreign feed popularly used by fish farmers. Therefore, fish farmers in Kwara State should be trained on maggot production, preservation and utilization.
2. Fish farmers are advised to look into their environment and harness the waste such as dead chick/chicken, blood meals gotten from abattoir etc. that can be fed to fish to reduce the cost of production in order to make fish farming a lucrative business in Kwara State.
3. Seminars and trainings on modern technologies on improved fingerlings/juvenile and improved fish feeds should be made available to the fish farmers in Kwara State.

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